

CHARGE AND STABILITY OF COLLOIDS. PART I ADSORPTION OF OPPOSITELY CHARGED IONS UNDER DIFFERENT CONDITIONS

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The amount of the precipitating ion adsorbed to neutralise the charge on a colloid has been measured. A distinction has been drawn between "chemical adsorption" which is the amount of the precipitating ion required to neutralise the charge on a colloid alone, and the "physical adsorption" which is the amount of the precipitating ion adsorbed by the coagulum. In an ordinary coagulation experiment by an electrolyte, the amount of the precipitating ion, which is carried down, is the sum total of these two. From the amount of the "chemical adsorption" alone, the charge on the colloidal particles has been calculated by a method similar to that used by Burton with certain modifications.

Various authors (Weiser, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 255; Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 326) have said that the amount of the precipitating ion carried down by the coagulated mass of a colloid is due to (a) the amount of adsorption necessary to produce charge neutralisation and (b) the adsorption by the electrically neutral particles during the process of agglomeration.

Burton (*Phil. Mag.*, 1906, 12, 425) attempted to measure the charge on a colloid by finding out the amount of aluminium ions adsorbed by a given amount of a silver colloid. The method employed was to measure the cataphoretic velocity of the colloidal particles when different concentrations of $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ were added to the sol. The silver particles ceased to move towards the anode and began to move towards the cathode. Burton determined the critical concentration of the aluminium ions required for coagulation by plotting the curve and noting graphically the critical concentration of aluminium ions when the velocity was zero. Here Burton assumed, as pointed out by Lewis, that the whole of the aluminium was adsorbed by the colloid. He also neglected the adsorption under (b). Lewis has calculated the charge from Burton's data and found it to be 28×10^{-2} e. s. u.

By utilising the Helmholtz-Lamb theory of double layer, Lewis (*Kolloid Z.*, 1909, 4, 211) has determined the charge on an oil-emulsion in water by measuring the velocity of the particles under a potential gradient, and he obtained the value $e = 4 \times 10^{-4}$ e. s. u. Again taking platinum colloid in water, Lewis has calculated e to be 8×10^{-3} e. s. u., by applying Lamb's equation to Burton's results. Lewis admits that the value of d , the thickness of the double layer, taken from Helmholtz's approximate value, may increase as much as ten times which certainly would reduce the value of e by ten times. Lewis made another attempt to determine the value of e by applying Stoke's law to the motion of the colloidal particle in an electric field. Taking the case of a silver colloid and utilising Burton's data, Lewis found $e = 8 \times 10^{-6}$ e. s. u. There is no doubt, therefore, that Burton's result for silver particles calculated from the adsorption of Al^{+++} ions is much too large.

The high value obtained by Burton may be due to the following two causes :

(i) He assumed that all the aluminium ions added to coagulate the colloid were adsorbed. Here it is necessary to determine the actual adsorption of the coagulating ions.

(ii) In calculating the charge by Burton's method it is also necessary to take into account the adsorption due to the first cause only and not due to the second.

Dhar (*loc. cit.*) has assumed that the adsorption under (*b*) is due to the residual affinity of the uncharged surface. Whilst this factor is the main cause, others may also produce adsorption, such as ions used in mechanically blocking the pores and entrainment of precipitating ions during agglomeration (Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Ghosh, *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1935, 1, 47).

In our experimental calculations of the amounts of adsorption under (*b*) we have not taken into consideration the adsorption due to these other factors—which is bound to be small.

The diffused double layer consists of the ionised part of the ion pairs at the surface together with diffused ionised portion in the dispersion medium, a part of which is osmotically active. The portion of the double layer held on the surface gives a net charge to the colloid and was originally assumed to be responsible to give stability. Conditions of unstability were studied by following the variations in the charge on the surface.

We have measured the adsorption of ions of an added electrolyte which carry a charge opposite to that of the colloid. In effect the adsorption of these oppositely charged ions releases other ions of the same sign from the counter part of the double layer. A quantitative relation between the adsorbed ions and the ions displaced may or may not exist. In subsequent parts of this series it has been found out that no simple relation exists between the amount of the added ions and the quantity of the released counter ions. It must, however, be pointed out that the ions released may not all come from the counter part of the double layer. Some of them may even be released from the surface of the colloid where they might be electrically held.

But in this paper, while calculating the charge, it has been assumed that the adsorbed ions displace all the ions of the same sign which form the outer portion of the double layer and thus the amount of the oppositely charged ion adsorbed is a measure of the amount of ions in the primary adsorbed layer.

We are fully alive to the limitations of the above assumptions but the order of the charge determined bears a close relation to the order of the charge determined by other methods. The aim of this paper is to show that with suitable precautions, which may be only a first approximation, a method depending on the basic idea of Burton may be evolved which gives results in conformity with the results obtained by other methods.

The adsorption taking place under (*a*) which is due to charge neutralisation, has been termed "chemical adsorption" and that taking place under (*b*) has been termed "physical adsorption". We are aware that expressions "chemical and physi-

cal adsorptions" have been used in different senses than stated above, e.g., "chemical adsorption" in the sense of chemisorption of Zsigmondy and "physical adsorption" in the sense of mechanical blocking of the pores. Our reason for calling the adsorption under (a) as the "chemical adsorption" is that adsorption which takes place here is due to charge neutralisation, and in case of adsorption as well as peptisation, a close relationship is present if not a too rapid change takes place from electrostatic to pure chemical combination" (Kolthoff, "Mass Analyse", I. p. 167).

In calculating the charge on a colloid we have tried to eliminate the adsorption under (b) by estimating the adsorption with freshly prepared and thoroughly washed neutral precipitates originally produced in the presence of electrolytes. While this gives a large amount of adsorption taking place under (b) during coagulation, the procedure is not free from inherent defects. In the first place, the adsorption by surfaces during the course of formation is bound to be greater than when they have been formed. Moreover, the amount of the neutral surface during coagulation is bound to be more than in an equal weight of freshly formed precipitate. Due to the above causes adsorption under (b) should be more than the adsorption by the freshly formed precipitate. Also, the use of KCl with ferric hydroxide sol and of HCl with As_2S_3 sol to produce the fresh precipitates is not free from difficulties. During coagulation oppositely charged ions from these electrolytes are adsorbed and it is just possible that they might not be completely removed by washing even when the filtrate shows no sign of them. This will certainly produce a lesser amount of the so-called "physical adsorption" under (b). In spite of these difficulties we are of opinion that the experimental procedure gives good results as a first approximation, and certainly gives a very fair idea of "chemical adsorption" under various conditions as the defects in determining "physical adsorption" are common to all experiments.

Recently in addition to chemical method, E. M. F. measurements and radio-active indicators have been used by Freundlich (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, 141, 249) and Kolthoff (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 2657) to measure the amount of adsorption by colloids. In the case of E. M. F. method, activities instead of concentrations were taken into consideration while determining adsorption. This involves difficulties. Moreover, this method has its limitations and cannot be used accurately for all the electrodes. The radio-active indicator method gives a result which can be accurately determined within 2% of the total adsorption (Kolthoff and Rosenblum, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933 55, 2657). Adsorption indicators also give results within 2%. The chemical analysis can be made quite sensitive when the amount of the material used is sufficiently large. The radio-active indicators are very useful when adsorption is to be determined from a very dilute solution, but in cases in which solutions are sufficiently concentrated, analytical methods are quite satisfactory.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

A large volume of colloidal solution (500 c. c.) was taken and the portion of the precipitating ion that was adsorbed was determined by chemical analysis at the coagulating concentration. The part of the precipitating ion that was thus adsorbed represented the total adsorption. The "physical adsorption" was determined by

taking an equal amount of the sol and precipitating by adding HCl to As_2S_3 and KCl to $Fe(OH)_3$ sol. and then thoroughly washing it till free from chlorine, and adding the calculated amount of the coagulating electrolyte and other ingredients where necessary and determining the amount of the precipitating ion adsorbed by the coagulum. under the same conditions as in the coagulation experiments.

Preparation of the Colloidal Solutions.— As_2S_3 sol was prepared by dissolving Kahlbaum's analytically pure arsenious oxide in freshly distilled water so as to give a concentration of the sol of about 15 to 20 g. per litre. The solution was filtered and a slow current of H_2S was passed till saturated. Excess of H_2S was removed by passing a current of pure hydrogen

Ferric hydroxide sol was prepared by dissolving chemically pure ferric chloride (50 g) in 4 litres of distilled water to which dilute ammonia was added drop by drop. The solution was shaken after addition of each drop of ammonia. till the solution was just short of precipitation. The sol was then kept for dialysis.

The concentration of As_2S_3 sol was determined directly by evaporating 10 c. c. of the sol in a silica crucible by keeping in an electric oven at 110° and weighing.

The ferric oxide in 25 c. c. portion of the sol was coagulated by ammonia, and the precipitate was collected, washed, ignited and weighed in the usual manner. The dialysed $Fe(OH)_3$ sol was used in the course of this investigation. The chlorine content of 25 c. c. portion of the sol was obtained first by adding a certain quantity of halogen free nitric acid and heating. This process dissolves the oxide leaving a precipitate of silver chloride. After this the silver salt was collected in a sintered crucible dried at 110° in an electric oven and weighed (*cf. Weiser, J. Phys. Chem., 1931, 35, 7*).

Determination of the Coagulating Concentration of the Electrolytes.—From a series of preliminary experiments, the coagulating concentrations of the electrolytes were determined by taking 5 c. c. of the sol and adding to it the necessary quantity of the coagulating electrolyte. keeping the total volume of sol and electrolyte 10 c. c. by the addition of the requisite amount of water.

Similar experiments were performed with $Fe(OH)_3$ sol using K_2SO_4 as the coagulating electrolyte.

Determination of the Chemical and Physical Adsorption of the Precipitating Ion.— As_2S_3 sol (500 c. c.) was taken and the requisite amount of $N/20$ - $BaCl_2$ added just to coagulate the sol in an hour. The total volume of the sol and the electrolyte was always made up to 1000 c. c. with distilled water. This was allowed to stand for an hour, after which the sol was filtered off carefully, and the precipitating ion in the supernatant liquid was estimated. Barium was estimated as $BaSO_4$ in the case of As_2S_3 sol by the usual method.

Similarly in the case of $Fe(OH)_3$ sol, 100 c. c. of the sol in (A) and 250 c. c. in (B) were taken and the electrolyte necessary to coagulate in an hour was added as determined from the preliminary experiments. The total volume in (A) was made up to 200 c. c. and in (B) 500 c. c. with distilled water.

Again 500 c. c. of the As_2S_3 sol, and 100 c. c. of the $Fe(OH)_3$ sol in (A) and 250 c. c. in (B) were taken in different flasks. The As_2S_3 sol was coagulated by

HCl and the coagula washed till free from chlorine. The whole of the precipitate was suspended in 500 c. c. of distilled water and the same concentration of the BaCl_2 solution as was necessary for the coagulation of an equal amount of the sol, as done above, was added. Here also the total volume of the suspension and the electrolyte was made up to 1000 c. c. This was also kept for an hour and filtered. After this the estimations of the precipitating ions were carried out exactly in the same manner as in the case of the respective sols. Similar experiments were done with $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol using KCl for coagulation.

Further, the As_2S_3 sol was stabilised by the addition of (a) pure sucrose, (b) pure glucose, and (c) H_2S solution of known concentration prepared in conductivity water. The ferric hydroxide sol was stabilised by the addition of dilute solution of known concentration of HCl.

In all these cases of the stabilised sols the amount of the "chemical adsorption" of the precipitating ion as well as the "physical adsorption" at the coagulating concentrations were determined exactly as stated above in presence of the added substances.

When H_2S was added to As_2S_3 sol, it was stabilised as shown by the higher coagulating concentration of the added electrolyte. This stabilisation caused an increased adsorption of the Ba ions. There was not a marked increase in the "physical adsorption" of the precipitating ion but there was a considerable increase in the "chemical adsorption". Exactly comparable experiments were carried out without the addition of H_2S solution.

Such experiments were also performed with $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol by first stabilising it by the addition of dilute HCl of known concentration, and then determining the adsorption of the precipitating ion. Exactly comparable experiments were done without the addition of HCl solution.

Determination of the Charge on each particle of As_2S_3 Sol and the Ferric Hydroxide Sol.—The "chemical adsorption" was determined by subtracting the "physical adsorption" from the amount of the total adsorption of the precipitating ion. This gave the total amount of the charge in the given quantity of the sol. The number of the particles in the sol was determined by finding out the radius of the As_2S_3 sol, by extrapolating the results of Börjeson (*Kolloid Z.*, 1920, 18, 27) who succeeded in determining the absolute size of the particle in a series of As_2S_3 sols obtained from As_2O_3 solutions of various concentrations. The density of the arsenious sulphide particles has been taken to be the same as in the bulk. From the mass of a single particle the number of the particles has been calculated in the amount of the colloid taken. Given the number of the particles and the total charge on them, the charge on each particle has been calculated by simple division. Detailed observations and calculations of a set of readings on As_2S_3 sol and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol are given in Tables I—III.

The charges at other concentrations and under different conditions of the respective sols have been similarly calculated and are given in Tables II and III.

TABLE I.

		As ₂ S ₃ sol, (500 c.c.)	Ferric Hydroxide sol, (100 c.c.)
Amount in the sol		11.23g. (As ₂ S ₃)	0.848 g. [Fe(OH) ₃]
Radius of the particles at above conc. ..		75 μ (by extrapolation)	50 μ
Vol. of each particle		1.768×10^{-16} c. c.	5.24×10^{-16} c.c.
Wt. of each particle		6.277×10^{-16} g.	1.834×10^{-16} g.
Average density of the mass		3.55 g. per c.c.	3.7 g. per c.c.
No. of the particles		1.799×10^{13}	4.37×10^{14}
Total adsorption of ions		0.0339 g. (Ba)	0.00533 g. (SO ₄ ²⁻)
"Physical adsorption" of ions		0.0049 g. ..	0.00047 g. (SO ₄ ²⁻).
"Chemical adsorption" of ions		0.0290 g. ..	0.00486 g. (SO ₄ ²⁻)
†Charge on each particle		$6.84 \times 2 \times 10^{-2}$ e.s.u.	6.70×10^{-2} e.s.u.

†Calculated as: $\frac{\text{Quantity of the charge in the amount of Ba or SO}_4^{2-} \text{ chemically adsorbed}}{\text{Number of the particles in the amount of the sol taken}}$

** Figures refer to 500 c. c. of the As₂S₃ sol.

* Figures refer to 100 c. c. of Fe(OH)₃ sol.

DISCUSSION

From the results given in Tables II and III, it is clear that the "chemical adsorption" of the precipitating ion increases when the sol is stabilised, (i) by the addition of an electrolyte such as H₂S to As₂S₃ sol and HCl to Fe(OH)₃ sol, or (ii) the addition of carbohydrates such as sucrose and glucose to the As₂S₃ sol. Under identical conditions the "physical adsorption" does not change to an appreciable extent; if at all, it shows a slight tendency to increase in both the above cases. Hence the explanation of Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 1253) that the stabilisation is due to the cutting down of the adsorption of the precipitating ion by the adsorption of the non-electrolytes is not substantiated. Sen (*Kolloid Z.*, 1926, 38, 310) has also reported an increase in the adsorption of the ions in presence of sugar.

The stability produced on adding minute traces of electrolytes to pure sols has been accepted by various observers as due to an adsorption of the similarly charged ions. Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) is of opinion that in the case of pure sols an initial low electric charge on the colloid indicates a low amount of primary adsorbed ions and it shall favour more primary adsorption of the ions carrying the same charge as the colloid. This view is supported by the fact that stabilisation usually occurs on the addition of uni-univalent salts. This adsorption necessarily produces an increase in the charge and an increase in the "chemical adsorption" observed in this case can be easily explained.

TABLE II.

Charge on arsenious sulphide sol.

AS₂S₃ sol taken = 500 c.c. Radius of the particle = 75 μ . Total vol. = 1000 c.c.
 Sol. conc. = 22.46 g./litre. No. of particles = 1.842 $\times 10^{14}$.
 Sucrose and glucose, 50 g each.

Sol. conc. = 24.72 g./litre. No. of particles = 1.968 $\times 10^{14}$.
 Sucrose and glucose, 150g. each.

Nature of sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba ions.		Charge in e. s. u.	Adsorption of Ba ions.		Charge in e. s. u.
		Total.	Phys.		Total.	Phys.	
Pure sol	50 c. c.	0.0339 g.	0.0049 g.	0.0290 g. 6.94 $\times 10^{-4}$	0.0355 g.	0.0053 g.	0.0302 g. 6.91 $\times 10^{-4}$
Sol. + sucrose	55	0.0394	0.0051	0.0343 8.09	0.0405	0.0055	0.0350 8.02
Sol. + glucose	55	0.0398	0.0052	0.0346 8.16	0.0411	0.0056	0.0355 8.13
Sol. + N/20-H ₂ S		0.0401	0.0052	0.0349 8.23	0.0415	0.0056	0.0359 8.24

with 20c. c. of N/20 - H₂S

with 30 c.c. of N/20 - H₂S

with 50 c.c. of N/20 - H₂S

TABLE III.

Charge on ferric hydroxide sol.

Radius of the particle = 50 μ
 Sol. B taken = 250 c.c.
 Cl content = 0.68 g./litre. Total vol. = 500 c.c.

Sol. A. taken = 100 c.c. Cl content = 0.84 g./litre. Total vol. = 200 c.c.

Sol. A. (conc. 8.478 g./litre) No. of particles = 4.97 $\times 10^{14}$
 Sol. B. (conc. 7.749 g./litre) No. of particles = 9.993 $\times 10^{14}$.

Nature of sol.	Total.	Adsorption of SO ₄ ⁻²		Charge in e. s. u.	Nature of sol.	Adsorption of SO ₄ ⁻²		Charge in e. s. u.
		Phys.	Chem.			Total.	Phys.	
Pure sol	0.005334	0.000474	0.004860	6.70 $\times 10^{-4}$	Pure sol	0.0124g	0.0015g	0.0109g.
"	0.00532	0.00047	0.00485	6.67	"	0.0123	0.0017	0.0106
"	0.00534	0.00048	0.00486	6.70	"	0.0125	0.0016	0.0109

N/20-K₂SO₄ added = 5.00 c. c. in 1 hr.

N/20-K₂SO₄ added = 6.00 c. c. in 1 hr.

N/20-K₂SO₄ added = 12.5 c. c. in 1 hr.

N/20-K₂SO₄ added = 15.0 c. c. in 1 hr.

Sol. + 2 c.c. of N/10-HCl	0.00670	0.00052	0.00618	8.52	Sol. + 5 c.c. of N/5-HCl	0.0156	0.0017	0.0139
"	0.00671	0.00052	0.00619	8.54	"	0.0160	0.0017	0.0143
"	0.00670	0.00056	0.00614	8.47	"	0.0152	0.0017	0.0135

But an increase in the "chemical adsorption" produced by the addition of non-electrolytes cannot be due to an increase in the charge on the particles on account of the adsorption of the similarly charged ions by them, because here no electrolyte is added. An actual increase in the value of the charge can take place by an increase in the dielectric constant or a decrease in the thickness of the double layer, according to the equation $e = VD/4\pi r^2$ provided the radius of the particle and the potential of the double layer remains the same. We agree with Mukherjee and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 704) that the potential of the double layer is not determined by the change in the dielectric constant, as Freundlich had assumed, and further it appears to us that the change in the value of the charge e , cannot be wholly explained by the change in the dielectric constant alone. It is rather more probable that the thickness of the double layer alters.

In this connection it is of importance to note that Wo. Ostwald (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, 42, 981) has pointed out that the "density of the charge instead of the magnitude of the charge" and the "compression of the double layer" might be responsible for the coagulation of a colloid; but certainly they are insufficient by themselves. Whether really an alteration in the thickness of the double layer is finally the cause of this increase in the concentration of the precipitating ion when the stabilisation is brought about by the addition of the non-electrolytes, further experiments can show. For the present it can only be taken as a suggestion.

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PYRIDINE COMPLEX OF METALLIC PERCHLORATES. PART I.

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Pyridine compounds of the perchlorates of silver, copper (ic), magnesium, calcium, strontium, barium, cadmium, zinc, mercury(ic), manganese, nickel and cobalt have been prepared. Compositions and characteristics of these compounds have been described. It has been found that the same pyridine compound is formed whether anhydrous or hydrated perchlorates are employed. No relationship seems to exist between the size of the metal atom or its ion and the number of pyridine molecules it can co-ordinate.

A large number of complex compounds of pyridine with various inorganic salts have been described in literature.* Most of the earlier investigations were,

* Jørgensen (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1884, ii, 33, 502). Veret (*compt. rend.*, 1892, 115, 464; 1897, 124, 1155). Klobb, *ibid.*, 1894, 118, 1271; Reitzenstein, *Annalen*, 1874, 282, 267; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1898, 19, 253. Pesci (*Gazzetta*, 1895, 25, 432). Pincoushn (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1897, 14, 385). Tombeck, (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1900, 21, 433; 1901, 22, 113). Litterscheid, (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1901, 239, 336; 1902, 240, 74). Grossmann (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 839), Pfeiffer and Pimmer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1905, 48, 98). Werner *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1908, 39, 1538). Davis and Logan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2497). Werner, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2577). Zvyagintsev, *et al.* (*Dokl. akad. sci., U.S.S.R.*, 1937, No. 3, p. 1255).